

DISTRIBUTION OF *BRANCHINECTA GAINI* (ANOSTRACA, BRANCHINECTIDAE) ON THE ISLANDS OFF THE WEST COAST OF ANTARCTIC PENINSULA BASED ON THE 28TH UKRAINIAN ANTARCTIC EXPEDITION (2023–2024)

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One of the most climate-sensitive ecosystems globally is the Antarctic terrestrial ecosystem, including its freshwater habitats. A notable representative of these freshwater ecosystems is the fairy shrimp *Branchinecta gaini* Daday, 1910, the largest freshwater invertebrate in Antarctica, with adults reaching lengths up to 16 mm. This species overwinters in the egg stage.

For a long time, *B. gaini* was considered an example of passive dispersal by birds, unlike most Antarctic terrestrial invertebrates, which survived the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) in glacial refugia. However, recent studies suggest this species also persisted in refugia during the LGM.

Previously, *B. gaini* was thought to be endemic to Antarctica. Still, research from the past decade has merged it with *Branchinecta granulosa* Daday, 1902, a species native to Patagonia (South America). As a result, the current distribution of *B. gaini* includes the Antarctic Peninsula, southern South America, and several sub-Antarctic islands such as South Georgia and the South Orkney Islands. Unfortunately, most studies do not specify the exact water bodies where this species is found, typically referring only to an archipelago or a particular island. This information is crucial for monitoring *B. gaini* distribution in the context of climate change.

The data presented in this study are based on 132 hydrobiological samples containing invertebrates collected from 42 freshwater bodies on the South Shetland Islands and the islands off the western coast of the Antarctica Peninsula during the 28th Ukrainian Antarctic Expedition (2023–2024). Samples were taken from the South Shetland Islands (Nelson Island, Deception Island, and King George Island), the Palmer Archipelago (Christine Island), the Wilhelm Archipelago (Irizar Island, Eight Island, Uruguay Island, Fanfare Island, Skua Island, Galindez Island, Grotto Island, un-named island of the Barchans, and Locator Island), the Pitt Islands (un-named island), and Marguerite Bay (Avian Island) from December 2023 to April 2024. Among the 42 studied freshwater bodies across 15

Antarctic islands, *B. gaini* was recorded in 28. On three islands: Nelson Island, Christine Island, and Eight Island, this crustacean is probably recorded for the first time.

In total, 2,294 individuals of *B. gaini* were identified. The samples varied greatly in both abundance and composition. In one sample (collected on February 2, 2024, on Irizar Island), 286 individuals were recorded, including 71 males, 69 females, and 146 juveniles.

It should be noted that *B. gaini* was not found in the studied freshwater bodies of the following islands: Deception Island, King George Island, Locator Island, Galindez Island, Grotto Island, Skua Island, an un-named island of the Pitt Islands (one reservoir was examined from each island), and Fanfare Island (two reservoirs were checked). The absence of *B. gaini* from certain islands highlights the necessity for further studies to clarify its range and habitat preferences, together with monitoring its response to climate change.